

PARTNERS

Zero Hidden Hunger EU brings together 19 partners from 12 European countries, including 14 universities and research centres, 3 non-profit organizations, 2 small and medium enterprises (SMEs) united to combat hidden hunger across Europe.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme (Grant Agreement No. 101137127) and is co-funded by UK Research and Innovation and the Swiss Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation.

CONTACT

Project coordinator

Kevin Cashman

✉ k.cashman@ucc.ie

University College Cork (Ireland)

Mairead Kiely

✉ m.kiely@ucc.ie

University College Cork (Ireland)

Communication contact

info@zerohiddenhunger.eu

Check out our social media!

#ZeroHiddenHungerEU

**ZERO
HIDDEN
HUNGER EU**

Reducing Micronutrient
Deficiencies

WHAT IS ZERO HIDDEN HUNGER EU?

Zero Hidden Hunger EU is a four-year project (2024-2028) addressing micronutrient deficiencies in Europe. The project will determine the true prevalence of these deficiencies and develop food-focused strategies to ensure adequate intake of vitamins and minerals.

KEY OBJECTIVES

MEASURE PREVALENCE

- Generate estimates of micronutrient deficiencies using biomarker and nutrient intake information from diverse European populations.
- Highlight the true extent of the issue, including associated healthcare costs and productivity losses, with a focus on marginalized and vulnerable groups.

PROVIDE EVIDENCE

- Equip policymakers and food system stakeholders with robust evidence to develop effective food-focused solutions aimed at eradicating micronutrient deficiencies in Europe.

DEVELOP STRATEGIES

- Create food-based strategies to ensure adequate micronutrient intake from sustainable sources.
- Utilise existing data and modelling to understand the root causes of micronutrient deficiencies across Europe.

WHY STUDY MICRONUTRIENT DEFICIENCIES?

Micronutrients are vitamins and minerals required in small amounts (milligrams or micrograms) for proper body function. They play crucial roles in every organ and body system, including energy production, immune function, brain development and function, skeletal growth and maintenance, and metabolism.

Each micronutrient has a dietary reference value, indicating the daily intake required to prevent deficiency and disease. A diet rich in nutrient-dense foods—such as fruits, vegetables, nuts, pulses, whole grains, vegetable oils, fish, meat, and dairy—can meet these requirements. No single food contains all micronutrients, making dietary variety essential.

When micronutrient intake falls short over time, deficiencies can develop, leading to health problems. Understanding the prevalence and distribution of these deficiencies is key to developing effective food-based solutions. This is the information gap that Zero Hidden Hunger EU aims to address in the coming years.